

GROWTH AND YIELD OF RICE VARIETIES (*Oryza sativa* L) AS INFLUENCED BY NITROGEN LEVELS IN THE NORTHERN ECOLOGICAL ZONE, FCT-ABUJA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Two field trials were carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja, in the growing seasons of 2021 and 2022 to determine the growth and yield of rice (*Oryza sativa*) varieties as influenced by nitrogen levels in the

Northern ecological zone at the blanket application of phosphorus and potassium. Five

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levels of Nitrogen (0kg/ha, 50kg/ha, 100kg/ha, 150kg/ha and 200kg/ha) and four rice varieties (Faro-44, Faro-66, Faro-67 and Gawal-R1). The experiment was designed as a 4x5 factorial combination within a randomised complete block design (RBCD) with 3 replications. A total of 60 plots were employed for the investigation, including 20

experimental plots in each replication. Data collected include Plant height, Number of leaves, Leaf Area (cm), Number of Tillers/stand and Grain Yield (t/ha). The data collected

were subjected to ANOVA using the R-statistics program, and where the treatment means were significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$), the Least Significant Difference (LSD) was used to separate them. The result showed that major variations in crop varieties and nitrogen application amounts affected crop performance at raising nitrogen levels increased at various growth stages and yield. The maximum grain yield was produced by Faro 67 with **Keywords:** Rice varieties, Nitrogen Fertiliser levels, Growth, Yields.

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an application of 100 kg/ha to 200 kg/ha throughout the trial years of 2021 and 2022, while the lowest was produced by Faro 44, which also produced the most tillers/stand at

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200 kg/ha. With nitrogen applied at 200 kg/ha, Gawal R1 yielded the highest grain yields (3.58 t/ha in 2021 and 5.5 t/ha in 2022).

1. INTRODUCTION

Rice, a semi-aquatic annual grass, stands as a global staple food and one of the most critical grains worldwide. Belonging to the genus *Oryza*, rice encompasses approximately 23 species. Of these, only two are commercially cultivated: *Oryza sativa* (Asian rice) and *Oryza glaberrima* (African rice). While *O. glaberrima* is exclusively cultivated in Africa, *O. sativa* is the predominant species grown globally (Vaughan et al., 2008). Environmental factors are paramount in influencing agricultural output, especially for rice cultivation (Onyegbula, 2017). Asia alone accounts for nearly 90% of the global *Oryza sativa* L. supply, critical for over half the world's population (Bandumula, 2018). Rice production significantly contributes to global food security, with China leading as both the largest producer and consumer. In recent decades, China has seen substantial increases in rice production and quality, attributed to advancements in breeding and cultivation techniques (Nie and Peng, 2017). Despite these gains, rice production is confronted by considerable challenges from unfavourable environmental conditions, both current and projected (Adhikari et al., 2015; Lv et al., 2018). Moreover, rapid climate change inherently threatens agroecosystems, agricultural productivity, and broader food security (Alidoost et al., 2019; Tonnang et al., 2022; Li, 2023). Rice cultivation is exceptionally water-intensive, consuming over 80% of Asia's irrigated freshwater resources (Bouman and Tuong, 2001). Both water and nitrogen (N) significantly influence crop yields (Ju et al., 2009). Over the past five decades, global rice yields have steadily risen, partly due to increased fertiliser nutrient inputs, especially nitrogen (Peng et al.,

2009, 2010). However, nitrogen fertiliser application is often inefficient, with an average apparent recovery efficiency of only about 33% (Garnett et al., 2009). Despite this inefficiency, nitrogen is indispensable for rice cultivation due to its crucial role as a component of essential cell constituents like plant hormones, nucleic acids, amino acids, ATP, and chlorophyll. Furthermore, it critically regulates numerous biochemical processes, including protein synthesis, carbon metabolism, and amino acid metabolism (Cai et al., 2012). Both excessive and insufficient nitrogen fertiliser application can significantly impair rice yield and quality (Manzoor et al., 2006). Thus, optimising fertiliser input is vital for achieving high grain production and maximising economic returns (Khuang et al., 2008). Ananthi et al. (2010) define the optimal mineral fertiliser quantity as that which maximises economic return at the lowest feasible cost. Effective crop nutrition management is therefore essential, enabling fertilisers to be applied efficiently and judiciously to significantly enhance rice yield and quality (Alam et al., 2009). Nitrogen application timing and rate are critical determinants of yield-contributing traits, as nitrogen promotes plant height, leaf size, panicle and spikelet numbers, and filled spikelets per panicle (Shakouri et al., 2012). Increasing local rice production has been rendered exceptionally challenging by numerous factors, particularly environmental constraints. Climate change, marked by rising temperatures and an increased frequency of extreme rainfall events (e.g., droughts and floods), poses a significant threat to crop yields, especially in tropical rain-fed agricultural systems (Furtak and Wolińska, 2023; MacCarthy et al., 2023).

As Nigeria's population continues to grow, so too is the demand for rice expected to increase. Each Nigerian is estimated to consume 40 kg of rice annually, a figure projected to rise. Despite 4.6 million hectares of potential rice cultivation land, only 1.7 million hectares are currently

~~Rice~~ (Sani et al., 2018).

staple food across both northern and southern Nigeria. In the northern and central regions of the subcontinent, even where maize is widely consumed, rice is prepared daily and for festivals and special events (Isaac *et al.*, 2014). However, local rice farmers consistently achieve yields of less than 2 to 2.5 tons per hectare, primarily owing to inadequate fertiliser application, especially nitrogen, despite improved cultivars having the potential to yield 8 to 10 tons per hectare (Imolehin and Wada, 2005).

Globally, chemical nitrogen (urea) fertiliser remains the most cost-effective means of soil amendment and agricultural yield enhancement. Nevertheless, improper use and management of nitrogen (urea) pose significant threats to crop productivity, environmental health, and human well-being. Insufficient soil nitrogen availability stems from various factors, including continuous cropping, erosion, leaching, plant uptake, poor land tenure structures, and population growth limiting arable land. Understanding varietal responses to differing nitrogen levels is crucial for guiding farmers in making informed fertiliser application decisions. Consequently, investigating optimal nitrogen levels is essential for maximising rice yield. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the responses of various rice types to differing nitrogen fertiliser rates, while maintaining consistent phosphorus and potassium dosages, to ascertain the optimal nitrogen

application for rice cultivation.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two field trials were carried out during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja, Nigeria, Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Gwagwalada is located on latitude

60° 45' and 70° 39' East and longitude 80° 25' and 90° 20' North. The average temperature was 30°C, 14% humidity during the rainy (planting) season and an annual rainfall between 1,100mm to 1,600mm (Idoko and Bisong, 2010).

The field evaluation experimental site was cleared, packed and stumped using machetes, rakes and dibbers.

Subsequently, the site was ploughed, harrowed and pulverised into a fine tilth. Beds of 2m x 2m were marked out using pegs 60 cm long. The experimental material used was four varieties of Rice (Farro 44, Farro 66, Farro 67 and Gawal R1 and the experimental treatment of which effects were evaluated are five

levels of nitrogen namely 50kg/ha⁻¹ (N1), 100kg/ha⁻¹ (N2), 150kg/ha⁻¹ (N3), 200kg/ha⁻¹ (N4) and 0kg/ha⁻¹ (N5). Phosphorus and Potassium were applied at 45kg per hectare as a blanket application using NPK15:15:15.

A factorial treatment arrangement fitted into a Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 3 replicas was used. Each replicate contained 20 plots; thus, a total of 60 plots were used in the experiment. Each Plot measured 2m x 2m and was separated from the other within the replicate by a 0.5m pathway. Each replicate was separated from the other by a one-meter (1m) alley for easy assessment of the experiment in the field. Using the dibbling method, after germination,

thinning was done to four seedlings per stand at a spacing of 30 cm x 30 cm, as recommended by the National Agricultural Seed Council (NASC), resulting in a plant population of 111,111.11 stands/ha. Weeding was done manually using a hoe at 4 and 8 weeks after sowing (WAS). Two split applications of the fertiliser were done 3 WAS, using the broadcast method of application. NPK (15:15:15) at 45 kg/ha was applied as the first dose, and the second dose from 5kg/ha, 55kg/ha, 105kg/ha and 155kg/ha of Urea was applied. The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the 'agricolae' package in the R Statistical Programme (version 4.5.0).. Where the treatment means were significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$), the Least Significant Difference (LSD) was used to separate them. Where significant interactions exist, the Least Squares Means (LSMEANS) was calculated and their level of significance was determined using their standard errors (SE) and P values ($p \leq 0.05$). Correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between yield and other agronomic parameters measured.

3. RESULTS

Tables 1 and 2 illustrate the influence of varying nitrogen levels on the plant height of specific rice varieties during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons. In the 2021 trial, optimal plant height was observed with higher nitrogen application. At 8 weeks after seeding (WAS), plants receiving 200 kg N ha⁻¹ achieved the greatest height (100.83 cm), a result statistically comparable to applications of 100 kg N ha⁻¹ and 150 kg N ha⁻¹.

Conversely, the shortest plants (83.85 cm) were found in plots treated with 50 kg N ha⁻¹, although this was not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) from control plots (0 kg N ha⁻¹). By 12 WAS, the trend continued, with 200 kg N ha⁻¹ still producing the tallest plants (116.82 cm). This height was statistically similar to those achieved with 100 kg N ha⁻¹ (109.08 cm) and 150 kg N ha⁻¹ (107.28 cm). The lowest plant heights at 12 WAS were recorded in plots with 50 kg N ha⁻¹ (97.08 cm) and control plots (99.45 cm). In 2022, a similar overall pattern in plant height was observed concerning nitrogen application. However, unlike 2021, plant heights remained relatively constant regardless of fertiliser application at 12 WAS in both trials, showing no significant difference. Throughout both seasons, plant heights varied significantly among the rice varieties, with Ferro 67 consistently being taller than Ferro 44, Grawal R1, and Ferro 66, which exhibited similar heights. Fertiliser-by-variety interaction (F_xV) was significant ($P \leq 0.05$) at 8 WAS in both the 2021 and 2022 experiments. Table 2 further details specific interactions between fertiliser levels and varieties. The highest recorded plant height of 120.23 cm resulted from the interaction between FARRO 67 and 200 kg N ha⁻¹ application, while the lowest (72.76 cm) was observed with GAWAL R1 combined with 50 kg N ha⁻¹. Additionally, within the same table, another set of results indicates that FARRO 67 with 100 kg N ha⁻¹ produced a maximum plant height of 50.03 cm, whereas GAWAL R1 with 50 kg N ha⁻¹ yielded the minimum height of 30.96 cm.

Table 1: Plant height of selected varieties of rice as influenced by nitrogen levels in 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

Treatments		8 WAS	12 WAS
Year 2021	Fertiliser levels	90.33b	99.45
	0kg 50kg	c	97.60
	100kg 150kg	83.85c	109.0
	200kg	96.86a	8
		100.83a	107.82
	LSD (0.05%)	10.38a	NS
	Varieties	b	
	FARRO 67	103.13	122.29a
	FARRO 44	a	102.75b
	GAWAL R1	90.41b	97.00b
	FARRO 66	87.89b	102.15b
LSD (0.05%)	92	14.29	
Year 2022	Fertiliser levels	.29b	
	0kg 50kg	89.97	100.4
	100kg 150kg	0	8
	200kg LSD	85.8	96.47
	(0.05%)	3	108.1
		96.5	0
	Varieties	2	106.6
	FARRO 67	96.2	0 10
	FARRO 44	104.72a	114.79a
	GAWAL R1	89.99b	NS
	FARRO 66	NS	94.67
LSD (0.05%)	91.60b	102.54b	
Interaction	9.49	4.49	
FxV	*	NS	

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 2: The impact of fertiliser-crop variety interactions on the plant height of several rice types at 8 WAP in both cropping seasons.

Year	Varieties	Fertiliser Levels (F)				
		0kg/ha	50kg/ha	100kg/ha	150kg/ha	200kg/ha
2021	FARRO 67	95.46 ^{bcd}	95.53 ^{bcd}	99.66 ^{bc}	104.76 ^{ab}	120.23 ^a
	FARRO 44	98.06 ^{bcd}	81.20 ^{def}	99.50 ^{bc}	81.56 ^{def}	91.70 ^{bcd}
	GAWAL	88.70 ^{bcd}	72.76 ^f	84.03 ^{cdef}	102.76 ^{bc}	91.16 ^{bcd}
	FARRO 66	79.06 ^{def}	85.90 ^{def}	50.03 ^a	47.46 ^{ab}	100.23 ^{bc}
		LSD = 17.28				
2022	R1			38.96 ^{cdef}	33.43 ^{ef}	42.33
	FARRO 67	38.60 ^{cdef}	43.56 ^{abc}	39.70 ^{bcd}	41.90 ^{abcd}	41.93 ^{abcd}
	FARRO 44	37.33 ^{cdef}	41.30 ^{bcd}			
	GAWAL R1	36.60 ^{cdef}	30.96 ^f			34.80 ^{def}
	FARRO 66	40.76 ^{bcd}	36.86 ^{cdef}	44.40 ^{abc}	39.73	42.10 ^{abcd}
		LSD = 8.36				

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 3 illustrates the effect of varying nitrogen levels on rice tiller quantity during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons. In 2021, tiller production showed no significant response to nitrogen application at either 8 or 12 weeks after sowing (WAS) ($P > 0.05$). However, varietal differences were observed: GAWAL R1 produced 25.40 tillers at 8 WAS, a statistically significant count ($P < 0.05$) compared to FARO 67, FARO 44, and FARO 66, which exhibited statistical similarity at 12 WAS.

Conversely, the 2022 field trial demonstrated that increasing nitrogen levels led to a rise in tiller output. The highest tiller count per plant (33.75 at 12

WAS) was recorded at 150 kg nitrogen per hectare, though this was not substantially different from 200 kg (29.83 tillers/plant) or 100 kg (29.50 tillers/plant). Control plots had the lowest number of tillers per plant at 12 WAS (24.08). In the 2022 trial, overall varietal differences in tiller output were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$), and no discernible fertiliser-by-variety (F \times V) interaction was observed at 8 WAP. However, specific combinations did yield distinct results: the highest tiller count (31.00) was achieved by combining FARRO 67 with 50 kg/ha fertiliser, while the lowest (13.66) was observed with FARRO 44 at the same fertiliser level.

Table 3: Number of Tillers of selected varieties of rice as influenced by nitrogen levels in the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

Number of leaves		8 W AS	12 WAS
Treatments			
Year	Fertiliser		
2021	level	19.1	31.2
	0kg 50kg	7	5
	100kg 150kg	23.4	27.3
	200kg LSD	2	3
	(0.05%)	21.7	26.3
		5	3
	Varieties	23.5	28.5
	FARRO 67	19.60	35.7
	FARRO 44	22.1	30.4
	GAWAL R1	7 NS	30.4
	FARRO 66	c	7
	LSD (0.05%)	25.40	29.0
Year	Fertiliser	a	0
202	level	22.4b	29.8b
2	0kg 50kg	7 NS	7 NS
	100kg	22.7b	29.5b
	150kg	22.83ab	29.50a
	200kg LSD	26.17a	b
	(0.05%)	22.17b	33.75a
	Significance	6.77	29.83a
		NS	b 6.33
	Varieties		NS
	FARRO 67	20.0	26.6
	FARRO 44	0	7
	GAWAL	19.8	27.2
	R1 FARRO	0	7
	66 LSD	22.4	30.8
	(0.05%)	0	7
	Interaction	22.0	28.8
	FxV	7 NS	7 NS

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 4 details the impact of the fertiliser-rice variety (FxV) interaction on leaf area at 12 weeks after sowing (WAS) throughout the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons. The greatest leaf area (75.22 cm²) was observed with the interaction of FARRO 44 and 200 kg/ha fertiliser application, while the

lowest (35.94 cm²) resulted from the interaction of GAWAL R and 50 kg/ha fertiliser application. Regarding the number of leaves per plant, Table 4 indicates that varying nitrogen levels significantly impacted this parameter during the 2021 cropping season (P<0.05).

Plots treated with 200 kg/ha of nitrogen showed the most leaves per plant (77.50), though this was not statistically different from plots treated with 150 kg/ha of nitrogen (67.58 leaves/plant).

Conversely, in the 2022 cropping season, rice stands exhibited a strong and statistically significant response ($P < 0.05$) to different nitrogen fertiliser doses. While 200 kg/ha of nitrogen generated the highest number of leaves per plant at both 8 and 12 WAS, this effect was not significantly different from the 150 kg/ha and 100 kg/ha nitrogen levels. Furthermore, the number of leaves per plant at 8 and 12 WAS did not significantly differ between control plots and those treated with 50 kg/ha of nitrogen. Varietal adjustments themselves showed no meaningful effect on leaf count at 8 and 12 WAS in either cropping season.

In terms of interaction effects on the number of leaves, Table 4 presents two distinct sets of findings. One analysis shows that the interaction between FARRO 66 and 100 kg/ha fertiliser application resulted in the highest value (184.33), whereas the interaction between FARRO 67 and 0 kg/ha fertiliser application produced a low value of 79.33. Another observation for the number of leaves indicates that the interaction of FARRO 44 with 200 kg/ha fertiliser application yielded a high value (85.33), significantly contrasting with a notably lower value (39.33) observed for the interaction between FARRO 67 and 0 kg/ha fertiliser application.

Table 4: Number of leaves of specific rice varieties as impacted by fertiliser, nitrogen levels, and variety interactions in the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

Treatments		8 WAS	12 WAS
Year 2021	Fertiliser levels		
	0kg	126.	131.1
	5 0kg 10	75	7
	0kg 15 0kg	114.	112.2
	20 0kg LSD	42	3
	(0.05 %)	118.	146.1
	Significance	75	7
		123.	141.8
	Varieties	17	3
	FARRO 67	119.	144.9
	FARRO 44	75.12.	7
	GAWAL R1	104.N	128.4
	FARRO 66	83	7
	LSD (0.05%)	147.	147.1
	Interaction	13	3
Year 2022	FxV Fertiliser levels	138.	133.0
	0kg 50kg	00 N	0 NS
	100kg 150kg	S	
	200kg LSD		
	(0.05 %)	97.29b	107.83b
		92.58b	102.83b
	Varieties	139.00	140.00a
	FARRO 67	a	144.67a
	FARRO 44	134.50	156.83a
	GAWAL R1	a	26.16
	FARRO 66	146.33	
	LSD (0.05%)	122.26.	132.2
	Interaction	35	0
	FxV	119.1	129.4
		3	0
	120.9	131.4	
	3	0	
	125.5	135.8	
	3 NS	0 NS	

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 5 shows that, except for 0 kg/ha and GAWAL R1 and 100 kg/ha-1-FARRO 66 in the first and second cropping seasons, respectively, there was no discernible

difference in the number of leaves at 12 WAS from the interaction between FxV in either year.

Table 5: The combined impact of rice cultivars and fertiliser level on the number of leaves at 12 WAS in the 2021 and 2022 planting seasons.

Years	Varieties	Fertiliser Levels (F)				
		0kg/ha	50kg/ha	100kg/ha	150kg/ha	200kg/ha
2021	FARRO 67	97.33 ^{cf}	87.66 ^f	145.33 ^{abcde}	162.33 ^{abc}	174.66 ^{ab-}
	FARRO 44	139.00 ^{abcde}	121.00 ^{cdef}	130.33 ^{bcdef}	126.00 ^{bcdef}	126.00 ^{bcdef}
	GAWAL R1					141.00 ^{abcde}
	FARRO 66					138.00 ^{abcde}
		183.00 ^a	110.33 ^{cdef}	145.33 ^{abcde}	151.00 ^{abcd}	128.00 ^{bcdef}
		105.33 ^{def}	130.00 ^{bcdef}	163.66 ^{abc}		
LSD = 49.06						
2022	FARRO 67	89.33 ^g	101.33 ^{fg}	146.00 ^{abcde}	164.66 ^{abc}	159.66 ^{abcd}
	FARRO 44	114.33 ^{efg}	103.66 ^{fg}	130.00 ^{cdefg}	113.66 ^{efg}	185.33 ^a
	GAWAL R1	127.33 ^{cdefg}	105.66 ^{fg}	136.00 ^{bcdef}	129.00 ^{defg}	159.66 ^{abcd}
	FARRO 66					100.33 ^{fg}
LSD = 40.83						

Means with the Sameletter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Tables 6 and 7 present the rice leaf area data for the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons, detailing the effects of variety, varying nitrogen levels, and their interactions (F×V). Nitrogen levels showed a varied impact on leaf area across seasons. In 2021, nitrogen variations did not significantly ($P < 0.05$) alter leaf area at 12 WAS. However, in 2022, increasing nitrogen significantly ($P < 0.05$) enhanced rice leaf area at both 8 and 12 WAS. The maximum leaf area in 2022 was achieved with 100

kg/ha of nitrogen, with no discernible difference noted between 150 kg/ha and 200 kg/ha. Regarding the four rice varieties, their leaf area did not significantly differ in either the 2021 or 2022 cropping seasons. Interaction effects (F×V) on plant leaf area also varied seasonally: they were not significant ($P < 0.05$) at 8 WAS in 2021, but were significant ($P < 0.05$) at both 8 and 12 WAS in 2022.

Table 6: Leaf area of specific rice varieties as impacted by nitrogen levels, fertilizer, and variety interactions in the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

Treatment	8 WAS	12 WAS
Year		
2021		
Fertiliser levels		
0kg	4.14b	57.6
50kg	34.38b	1
100kg	45.29a	56.5
150 kg	45.92a	4
200kg	48.56	59.7
	LSD =9.19	1
Significance	NS	NS
Varieties		5
FARRO 67	44.97	59.87
FARRO 44	45.48	69.57
GAWAL R1	39.63	58.83
FARRO 66	42.15	53.82
LSD (0.05%)	NS	NS
Interaction		
FxV	NS	*
Year		
2022		
Fertiliser levels		
0kg	38.85b	51.81b
50kg	35.37b	47.17b
100kg	49.43a	65.90a
150kg	42.64ab	57.52ab
200kg	44.58a b	59.44ab
	NS	
Significance		NS
LSD (0.05%)	9.33	12.51
Varieties		
FARRO 67	44.92	59.89
FARRO 44	46.68	62.24
GAWAL R1	36.60	49.34
FARRO 66	40.50	54.00
LSD (0.05%)	NS	NS
Interaction		
FxV	*	*

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 7: The effects of fertilizer and rice variety interactions on leaf area at 12 WASS across the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Year	Varieties	Fertiliser levels (F)				
		0kg/ha	50kg/ha	100kg/ha	150kg/ha	200kg/ha
2021	FARRO 67	56.24 ^{abcd}	42.17 ^d	69.97 ^{ab}	69.59 ^{ab}	60.83 ^{abcd}
	FARRO 44	66.10 ^{ab}	59.75 ^{abcd}	48.53 ^{bcd}	50.97 ^{abcd}	72.98 ^a
	GAWAL R1	55.41 ^{abcd}	58.85 ^{abcd}	61.79 ^{abcd}	63.52 ^{abcd}	58.56 ^{abcd}
	FARRO66	52.68 ^{abcd}	58.85 ^{abcd}	58.51 ^{abcd}	54.50 ^{abcd}	43.06 ^{acd}
				LSD = 22.35		
2022	FARRO 67	50.95 ^{cde}	42.11 ^{de}	70.88 ^{abc}	74.93 ^{abcd}	60.58 ^{abcd}
	FARRO 44	48.92 ^{de}	62.93 ^{abcd}	74.18 ^{ab}	49.95 ^{de}	75.22 ^a
	GAWAL R1	53.33 ^{bcde}	35.94 ^e	55.87 ^{abcde}	55.75 ^{abcde}	45.78 ^{de}
	FARRO 66	54.02 ^{bcde}	47.67 ^{de}	62.68 ^{abcd}	49.44 ^{de}	56.16 ^{abcde}
				LSD = 20.90		

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

As shown in Table 8, nitrogen application rates had a significant ($P < 0.05$) impact on rice grain yield across varieties and the 2021–2022 cropping season. 200 kg of nitrogen was consistently the highest yield, reaching 3.58 t/ha in 2021 and 5.31 t/ha in 2022. Conversely, the control plots showed the lowest yields, with 1.94 t/ha and 1.92 t/ha for the corresponding

seasons, respectively. The 100 kg and 150 kg nitrogen levels for the two cropping seasons did not differ statistically in spite of these trends. Furthermore, there was a substantial interaction ($P < 0.05$) between fertilizer application and variety (F \times V), even though individual varietal differences had no discernible effect on production in either year.

Table 8: Grain yield (t/ha) of rice as impacted by various fertilizer levels, varieties, and F \times V interactions in the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

	2021	2022
Fertiliser levels		
0kg 50kg 100kg	1.94	1.92
150kg 200kg	2.08	2.73
LSD (0.05%)	3.04	5.21
	3.07	4.96
	3.58	5.31
	0.03	0.07
Varieties		
FARRO 67	3.08	4.47
FARRO 44	3.28	4.18
GAWAL R1	3.12	5.08
FARRO 66	3.21	4.68
LSD (0.05%)		
Significance		
F \times V	NS	NS
	*	*

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 9 indicates that in the 2021 cropping season, the maximum grain weight of 2.73 kg was obtained from the interaction of GAWAL R1 and 100 kg/ha of fertiliser application, while the lowest (1.10 kg) occurred with FARRO 67 and no fertiliser.

Table 9: Interaction of FxV on Grain Weight in 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

Variety (V)	Fertiliser levels (F)				
	0kg/ha	50 kg / h a	100kg/ha	150kg/ha	200kg/ha
F arro 67	1.10 ^d	1.43 ^{bcd}	2.03 ^{abcd}	2.43 ^{ab}	1.93 ^{abcd}
Farro 44	1.43 ^{bcd} 2.03	1.56 ^{bcd}	1.90 ^{abcd}	1.26 ^{cd}	2.20 ^{abc}
Gawal R1	^{abcd}	1.40 ^{cd}	2.73 ^a	2.00 ^{abcd}	2.00 ^{abcd} 2.36
Farro 66	1.70 ^{bcd}	1.56 ^{bcd}	1.80 ^{abcd}	2.06 ^{abc}	^{ab}

LSD = 0.94

Means with the same letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

4. DISCUSSION

In both trials, plants treated with 200 kg of nitrogen showed the greatest height after 8 weeks of sowing (WAS), although this was not significantly different from treatments with 100 kg and 150 kg of nitrogen. In stark contrast, control plots had relatively short stands, strongly indicating the vital role of nitrogen in vegetative plant growth. This observation aligns with Gewaily *et al.* (2021), who reported that nitrogen fertiliser promotes plant growth, particularly by lengthening and increasing internodes, resulting in taller plants. The reduced growth seen in the control plots can therefore be attributed to a lack of nitrogen. Similar findings of stunted plant growth due to nitrogen deficiency have also been documented for sorghum (Jaham, 2014). At 8 weeks after sowing, the height of rice seedlings in control plots was comparable to those receiving 50 kg of nitrogen, suggesting that 50 kg of nitrogen was insufficient to stimulate significant rapid growth. Notably, considerable variation in plant height was observed among the four

rice varieties. Farro 67 consistently exhibited greater height across both cropping years, regardless of nitrogen application. This could be attributed to superior nutrient conversion efficiency, enhanced nutrient uptake, or increased competitiveness against weeds. Furthermore, a significant Genotype x Nitrogen (G x N) interaction on plant height was observed, indicating that the tested varieties responded differently to varying nitrogen levels. Tiller production generally increased with rising nitrogen levels. The highest number of tillers per plant was observed at 150 kg/ha of nitrogen, although this was not significantly different from treatments at 100 kg/ha and 200 kg/ha. This suggests that a nitrogen application rate of up to 100 kg/ha is sufficient or optimal for robust tiller production. Correspondingly, a decrease in nitrogen supply led to fewer tillers, a finding consistent with other research (Huang *et al.* 2013; Deiss *et al.* 2014) and evident in the lowest tiller counts observed in the control plots. Significantly,

tiller production did not vary substantially among the four rice varieties investigated. This indicates that varietal differences did not influence the rice plant's response to applied nitrogen regarding tillering, as evidenced by the non-significant Genotype x Nitrogen (G x N) interaction at both 8 and 12 WAS in the 2022 trial. In the second trial, nitrogen application significantly influenced rice leaf production. The highest number of leaves per plant was observed with 200 kg of nitrogen, whereas leaf production in the control plots was comparable to that at 50 kg of nitrogen. In all, nitrogen application demonstrably increased both rice leaf area and leaf productivity. This enhancement of individual plant leaf area, in turn, boosts the overall Leaf Area Index (LAI) per unit land area (Herve, 2017), thereby facilitating greater photosynthetic activity in the crops. Consistent with other measured characteristics, leaf area production did not significantly differ among the four rice varieties used in this study.

Grain yield of rice as influenced by varieties and varying nitrogen levels

Nitrogen application consistently increased rice grain production. Generally, nitrogen-based fertilisers are considered more effective at enhancing crop yields than those containing phosphate or potassium. Nitrogen application significantly influences various growth and yield parameters, including dry matter, harvest index, oil content, seed yield per plant, and other yield components (Ibrahim *et al.* 2022). In both trials conducted, the maximum grain yields (3.58 t/ha) were achieved with 200 kg of nitrogen. This finding contrasts with Ibrahim (2022), who suggested a lower rate of 46–100 kg N/ha for optimal yield.

Conversely, Aminul *et al.* (2015) recommended that nitrogen application should not exceed 150–200 kg per hectare, concluding that the ideal dosage was 150–200 kg N/ha combined with 118 kg P₂O₅/ha. Control plots consistently exhibited the lowest grain yields, likely attributable to the unequal fertility of the trial site. While variations in rice variety did not substantially affect grain yield, indicating no single variety outperformed others, a strong interaction between fertiliser and varieties suggested that different types of rice responded distinctly to nitrogen application.

5. CONCLUSION

Nitrogen application proved highly effective in boosting rice yield and growth, with the optimal rate of 200 kg/ha delivering a maximum grain yield of 3.58 t/ha. High nitrogen levels (150–200 kg/ha) were particularly effective in promoting vegetative development, leading to taller plants and more tillers, which underscores the necessity of customised fertiliser approaches. Among the varieties tested, FARO 44 and GAWAL R1 consistently yielded the best results, though other varieties responded differently to nitrogen. For farmers in the Northern Ecological Zone, FCT-Abuja, Nigeria, it is advised to use the Farro 67 rice variety and apply 150–200 kg/ha of nitrogen fertiliser to achieve maximum growth and productivity. To further refine these recommendations and ensure widespread adoption, additional research is required to determine precise nitrogen levels for specific varieties and soil types, coupled with government support for farmer training and guidance on best practices.

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